

The Reflow of Semi-Cured Material

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Motivation

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Mode I DCB Fracture Surfaces

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Initial Rheological Experiments

In-Situ Testing

- Custom 450/225 kVp Hutch in μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre used for In-Situ characterisation.
- Custom UoB heating rig developed in BCI used.

NXCT | National X-Ray
Computed
Tomography

University of
Southampton

In-Situ Testing

In-Situ Testing

In-Situ Results – Medium α

In-Situ Results – Low α

Conclusions

- The possibility of resin reflow in partially cured material showed using rheological experiments
- Reflow/Press has now been demonstrated in-situ using X-CT
- Future work to analyse the 3d flow front underway to fully leverage the 3D data captured in the CT data

Thank you!

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